

Kinetics and mechanism of complex formation between gallium(III) and *trans*-bis[(en)₂Co(H-malonato)₂]⁺ in aqueous medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of reversible complexation between gallium(III) and title cobalt(III) complex, *trans*-bis[(en)₂Co(malH)₂]⁺, have been investigated using stopped flow technique at 25 °C, 0.1 ≤ [H⁺], ≤ 0.3, 0.001 ≤ [Ga³⁺], ≤ 0.005 and I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³. A general mechanism is proposed which accounts for the available data on the formation of binuclear species involving mainly the reaction of Ga³⁺ with dissociated form of the Co^{III} complex. The pseudo-first order rate constants increased linearly with the increase of [Ga³⁺]_T at a fixed acidity indicating the formation of 1 : 1 binuclear complex formed between Ga^{III} and conjugate base of Co^{III} complex. Comparing the derived rate parameters with water exchange rate constant of Ga(OH)₂³⁺ and with several analogous systems, it is concluded that the mechanism of substitution reaction at Ga³⁺ centre is more likely to be I_a. The rate of spontaneous dissociation of the binuclear complex has also been reported.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, stopped flow, gallium(III), cobalt(III) complexes.

The kinetics of reversible complexation between transition metal ions and a variety of ligands have been extensively studied in last few decades because of their wide applications in biological, analytical and extractive metallurgical processes¹⁻³. Complexation reactions of trivalent metal ions like iron(III) with a variety of unbound and partially bound ligand has been a subject of large number of investigations¹⁻⁷. In comparison, such reaction with non-transition metal ion Ga^{III} has been limited to few studies⁸⁻¹⁴ primarily due to lack of non-protic ligands reacting with Ga^{III} and also due the facile hydrolysis of Ga^{III} ion which leads to proton ambiguity. These studies includes the unbound ligands containing phenolic OH group viz. salicylic acid and their nitro derivatives⁸, 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol⁹, 4-nitrocatechol¹⁰ etc. as well as new hexadentate siderophore¹¹. In most of the cases the kinetic data are in consistent with the I_d mechanism for ligand substitution at (OH)Ga(H₂O)₅²⁺.

Keeping these in view and as a sequel to our previous studies on complexation of bivalent and trivalent metal ions with a variety of partially bound carboxylates/aminocarboxylates³⁻⁶ and ¹³⁻¹⁶, we report here the complexation of Ga^{III} with the title cobalt(III) complex. The primary aim of this work is to know whether substitution reaction of Ga^{III} (aq) follow I_d or I_a path.

Results and discussion

Acid dissociation constants : The potentiometric titration of the complex showed equivalence point corresponding to neutralisation of two protons according to eq. (1).

The average values of pK₁ and pK₂ were found to be 3.25 ± 0.08 and 4.04 ± 0.07 (I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³) which compare well with those reported previously (pK₁ = 3.0 ± 0.1 and pK₂ = 4.1 ± 0.1 at 25 °C and I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³)¹⁷ and (pK₁ = 3.3 ± 0.01 and pK₂ = 4.0 ± 0.02 at 30 °C and I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³)¹⁸.

Reversible formation of binuclear complex : The spectra of malonato complex in the absence and presence of gallium(III) are presented in Fig. 1 which clearly indicate its interaction with the added metal ion. Rate data for the formation of binuclear species, are collected in Table 1. The formation reaction was studied at [H⁺]_T = 0.1–0.3 mol dm⁻³ in order to avoid appreciable hydrolysis of Ga(OH)₂³⁺ (pK_h = 2.94 at 25 °C, I = 0.5 mol dm⁻³) and polymerization of GaOH²⁺. Under these conditions the deprotonated form of cobalt substrate, [Co(en)₂(malH)mal] will be appreciable (pK₁ = 3.25 ± 0.08, pK₂ = 4.04 ± 0.07 for *trans*-

Table I. Rate constants and derived rate parameters for the complexation of Ga^{III} with (en)₂Co(O₂CCH₂CO₂H)₂⁺ at 25 °C, I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

10 ³ [Ga ³⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹) at [H ⁺]				
	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30 mol dm ⁻³
1.0	2.81 ± 0.05	2.68 ± 0.07	2.57 ± 0.06	2.50 ± 0.08	2.40 ± 0.07
2.0	3.35 ± 0.15	3.10 ± 0.08	2.95 ± 0.07	2.75 ± 0.14	2.58 ± 0.11
3.0	3.86 ± 0.11	3.51 ± 0.19	3.30 ± 0.18	3.11 ± 0.10	2.85 ± 0.08
4.0	4.54 ± 0.14	4.12 ± 0.16	3.62 ± 0.16	3.45 ± 0.14	3.18 ± 0.18
5.0	5.25 ± 0.21	4.48 ± 0.23	4.02 ± 0.18	3.71 ± 0.18	3.41 ± 0.15
<i>k</i> _r (dm mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	615	469	377	309	270
<i>k</i> _r (s ⁻¹)	2.12	2.18	2.17	2.20	2.08

[Co(en)₂(O₂CCH₂CO₂H)₂]⁺ at I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³). It is evident that the pseudo-first order rate constants increases linearly with the increase in [Ga^{III}]_T at a fixed acidity resulting in a constant finite intercept for *k*_{obs} versus [Ga³⁺]_T plots at [H⁺] = 0.1–0.3 mol dm⁻³ (see Fig. 2). It is therefore, reasonable to assume that the acid dependence of the reaction results only from the Ga(OH₂)₆³⁺/Ga(OH₂)₅OH²⁺ and coordinated malonate conjugate base equilibrium. The slopes of such plots, however, vary inversely with [H⁺]_T. The observed first order dependence of *k*_{obs} with [Ga³⁺]_T is indicative of the fact that only (1 : 1) binuclear complex is formed between Ga^{III} and the cobalt(III) substrate.

The possible reaction mechanism consistent with the observed facts can be delineated as in Scheme 1,

Fig. 1. Spectral evidence for the formation of binuclear species between Ga^{III} and trans-[(en)₂Co(malH)₂]⁺ ions at [H⁺] = 0.1 m, I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³: (A) [Ga³⁺] = 4 × 10⁻³, (B) [complex] = 5 × 10⁻⁴ and [Ga³⁺] = 4 × 10⁻³ + [complex] = 5 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³.

Fig. 2. Plots of *k*_{obs} versus [Ga³⁺] for the formation of binuclear complex between (en)₂Co(O₂CCH₂CO₂H)₂⁺ and Ga³⁺ at varying acid concentrations: (1) 0.1, (2) 0.15, (3) 0.2, (4) 0.25 and (5) 0.3 mol dm⁻³.

The rate law (eq. (2)) is consistent with the above mechanism.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = (k_1 + k_2 K_h / [\text{H}^+]) \left(\frac{K_1}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \right) [\text{Ga}^{3+}]_T + k_{-1} + k_{-2} K_h' / [\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

Since *K*₁ << [H⁺] the eq. (2) can be rewritten as eq. (3).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = (k_1 + k_2 K_h / [\text{H}^+]) \left(\frac{K_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) [\text{Ga}^{3+}]_T + k_{-1} + k_{-2} K_h' / [\text{H}^+] \quad (3)$$

At constant [H⁺], the slope and intercept of the *k*_{obs} vs [Ga³⁺]_T plot are

$$\text{Slope} = (k_1 + k_2 K_h / [\text{H}^+]) \left(\frac{K_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Intercept} = k_{-1} + k_{-2} K_h' / [\text{H}^+] \quad (5)$$

The slope and intercepts at different [H⁺] for the *k*_{obs} vs [Ga³⁺]_T plot are collected in Table 1.

In order to obtain the value of *k*₁ and *k*₂*K*_h, (slope) × [H⁺]_T/*K*₁ was plotted against [H⁺]⁻¹.

Table 2. Comparison of kinetic parameters with other related systems at 25 °C

System	Metal ion	k_1 ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	k_{-1} (s^{-1})	k_2 ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$k_2 K_h$ (s^{-1})	Ref.
Salicylate	Al ³⁺	9.1×10^{-1}	7.8×10^{-1}	1.02×10^3	–	23
<i>cis</i> -[Co(en) ₂ (NH ₂) ₂ O ₂ CC ₆ H ₃ (3-NO ₂)OH] ²⁺	Al ³⁺	(0.183 ± 0.003)	2.68×10^{-3}	–	–	24
*[(NH ₃) ₅ CoO ₂ CCO ₂ H] ²⁺	Al ³⁺	(2.47 ± 0.05)	$(5.0 \pm 1.0) \times 10^{-2}$	–	–	13
*[(NH ₃) ₅ CoO ₂ CCO ₂ H] ²⁺	Ga ³⁺	–	–	17.14×10^3	19.72 ± 0.06	13
*[(NH ₃) ₅ CoO ₂ CCO ₂ H] ²⁺	Fe ³⁺	11.0×10^2	0.7	4.8×10^3	–	6
*[(NH ₃) ₅ CoO ₂ CCO ₂ H] ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	$(3.99 \pm 0.12) \times 10^3$	89.6 ± 1	–	–	25
[(NH ₃) ₅ CoOCO(CH ₂) ₂ CO ₂ H] ²⁺	Ga ³⁺	0.780×10^2	1.87	17.84×10^3	20.52	14
[(en) ₂ Co(O ₂ CCH ₂ CO ₂ H) ₂] ⁺	Ga ³⁺	1.581×10^5	2.15 ± 0.05	–	–	This work

The slope of the above plot was found to be negative. Hence probably the GaOH²⁺ species is not active in the reaction. The intercept is equal to k_1 and is presented in Table 2. The intercept k_{obs} vs $[\text{Ga}^{\text{III}}]_T$ plot is virtually independent of $[\text{H}^+]$ (please see Table 1). Hence intercept is equal to k_{-1} . The average value of k_{-1} with standard deviation is presented in Table 2. The k_{ex} (25 °C) value for Ga(H₂O)₆³⁺ is found to be $3.9 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-19}$ and k_1 value for the above reaction is $1.58 \times 10^5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Much higher value of k_1 supports I_a mechanism for the reaction.

Experimental

Materials : *trans*-bis[(Hmalonato)₂bis(ethylenediamine)₂cobalt(III)] perchlorate was prepared by reported method¹⁷ and characterized as described earlier¹⁸. The purity of complex was further checked by estimation of Co^{III} by Laitinen and Burdett method²⁰. Gallium perchlorate was prepared and metal ion content and free acids were estimated adopting standard procedure^{21,22}. Ionic strength was adjusted with NaClO₄ solution. All chemicals used were of analytical grade and double distilled water was used for the preparation of stock solutions for kinetic studies.

Acid dissociation constants and kinetic measurements : The acid dissociation constants of title cobalt(III) complex were determined potentiometrically by following the method described earlier¹⁸. The pH measurements were made using a Elico CL54 digital pH meter after standardization with standard NBS buffers. All UV-visible measurements were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 20 spectrophotometer.

The kinetics of reversible complexation between gallium(III) and cobalt(III) substrate was followed at 25 °C, $\lambda = 280 \text{ nm}$ and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ using a Hi-Tech (UK) stopped flow spectrophotometer. Only a single exponential curve was displayed (with a decrease in absorbance with time) for every

run, even after displayed (with a decrease in absorbance with time) for every run, even after spreading the reaction over the time scale accessible by the instrument. The observed rate constants reported are average of at least five kinetic runs and the errors quoted are standard deviation.

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